

The Dharma and Bodhicitta – A Conflict Resolution

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Abstract

The age of reason vanquished religion therefore we need to recruit the religious consciousness. Our modern malaise produces a depressive scenario and in the post – modernist era, commodity forms have triumphed. Living in a purely materialistic time, people lead sleepy lives instead of being aware and awake. A widespread sense of ethical disarray, terror and destruction, depletion of natural resources and psychocatastrophes have resulted in a pandemic of suffering not to forget the human vulnerability to disease, old age and death. In such a condition, nothing is more needful than redemption of attention. Buddha taught us to develop our minds to the path of serenity, peace and enlightenment. He points to the three types of spiritual practitioners; the wise, the wiser and the wisest. The wise ones strive for happy future lives whereas the wiser ones will attempt to attain liberation from cyclic existence. The wisest, however, will opt to realize the ultimate goal of enlightenment for the benefit of all sentient beings.

Key Words: Buddhism, Dharma and Bodhicitta.

The antidote to delusion, ego and every other problem we face is the wisdom of Dharma. Dharma wisdom provides the deepest solution to every human problem. Whoever has problems needs Dharma; Dharma wisdom is the light that eliminates the dark shadow of ignorance, the main source of all human afflictions. Doctrine is not Dharma; religious art is not Dharma. Dharma is not that

statue of Lord Buddha on your altar. Dharma is the inner understanding of reality that leads us beyond the dark shadow of ignorance, beyond dissatisfaction.

It is not enough to accept Dharma as being true. We must also understand our individual reality, our specific needs and the purpose of Dharma as it relates to us as individuals. If we accept Dharma for reasons of custom or culture alone, it does not become properly effective for our minds. Dharma cannot solve our problems if we do not approach it pragmatically. You should seek Dharma knowledge in order to end your problems, to make yourself spiritually healthy – in religious terms, to discover eternal happiness, peace and bliss.

We ourselves are responsible for discovering our own peace and liberation. We cannot say that some other power, like God, is responsible – if we do, we are weak and not taking responsibility for the actions of our own body, speech and mind. Buddhists understand that they are personally responsible for everything they do, it's in their own hands to determine whether their actions are positive or negative.

One of the most fundamental Buddhist teachings is to renounce samsara. That doesn't mean we shouldn't drink water when we are thirsty. It means that we must understand samsara in such a manner that even when we are caught in a samsaric situation, no karmic reaction ensues.

That's why we call samsara a cycle: a cyclic existence. We do various things-we change and enjoy the novelty of every change- but actually, all we are doing is creating more karma. Every time we do something, there's a reaction that makes our bondage in cyclic existence even tighter than it was before. That's samsara. To loosen this tightness, we need the wisdom that illuminates the darkness of ignorance. It is important for us to recognize some of our habits and attitudes are wrong, it's possible to change and transform them. Grasping at permanence makes us think that we are unchanging. This negative thought pattern is very strong and prevents us from developing or acting according to Dharma. To help us overcome our wrong conceptions, Lord Buddha taught the Four Noble Truths. As the first characteristic of the noble truth of suffering, he taught impermanence.

It is very important to understand impermanence. When we understand the impermanent nature of things their non – stop change, we give ourselves the time and space to accept whatever situation comes along. Then even if we are suffering, we can take care of ourselves, we can look at it without getting upset. Otherwise, our upset or guilty mind prevents us from waking from confusion, from seeing our own clarity.

Clarity always exists within us. The nature of our consciousness is clear. It is merely a question of seeing it. If you always feel dirty, negative and hopeless, as if you're somebody who could never possibly discover inner peace and liberation, you're reacting to a deluded, negative mind, a fixed conception. You're thinking beyond reality, beyond the nature of phenomena; you're not in touch with reality. You have not eradicate such preconceived ideas before you can cultivate tranquillity and peace before your intelligence can touch reality.

The beauty of being human is that we can continuously develop inner qualities such as peace, the energy of the enlightenment experience and bliss, and eventually transcend your dualistic mind. When you come to understand this inner beauty, you will stop grasping at external objects, which can never bring eternal satisfaction. This is an important sign of spiritual progress. You cannot simultaneously be religious and grasp at material things i.e. the two are incompatible.

We see that people get more and more confused and dissatisfied, the more possessions they get, finally some of them commit suicide. Sometimes the poor don't understand this; they think that materially wealthy people must be happy. They are not happy. They are dissatisfied, emotionally disturbed, confused and immersed in suffering. Suicide rates are much higher in affluent societies than in economically undeveloped ones – this is present – day reality, it's happening right now. I am not suggesting that to give up our material comfort rather we should avoid confusing ourselves by grasping at all worldly pleasures.

The underlying attitude that forces us to chase after unworthy objects is the delusion that causes us to think, 'This object will give me satisfaction; without it life would be hopeless.' These preconceptions make us incapable of dealing with the new situations that inevitably arise from day to day. We expect things to happen in a certain way and when they don't, we can't cope with them properly. Instead of handling unexpected situations effectively, we become tense, frustrated and psychologically disturbed.

Most of us are emotionally unstable, sometimes up and sometimes down. When life is going well, we put on a very religious aspect, but when things go bad we lose it completely. This shows that we have no inner conviction, that our understanding of Dharma is very limited and fickle.

Are you satisfied with your present state of mind? Probably not, why you need Dharma. Worldly possessions do not give you satisfaction; you can't depend on transitory objects for your happiness.

Mental attitude is the main problem; physical problems are secondary. Therefore, avoid grasping at material objects and seek instead an indestructible understanding of the ultimate nature of the mind. However, in order to completely destroy the root of the dualistic mind, a partial understanding of the reality of our own mind is not sufficient. Dharma practice requires continual, sustained effort; just a few flashes of understanding are not enough. To fully penetrate the ultimate reality of our own mind, we have to develop single – pointed concentration. When we have done so, our understanding will be continuous and indestructible.

Lord Buddha's teachings on single – pointed concentration are very important because they show us how to transcend worldly conceptions. However, single –pointed concentration alone is not enough. We have to combine it with penetrative insight. What's the difference between the two ? First, we develop single – pointed concentration, which leads us beyond worldly emotional problem and gives us a degree of higher satisfaction. But a certain amount of darkness remains in our mind. In order to reach the depth of human consciousness, we also have to cultivate penetrative insight, which is the only thing that can lead us totally beyond the dualistic view of all existence. From the Buddhist point of view, the dualistic way of thinking is the real conflict. Meditative concentration can bring us a certain degree of peace, but the dualistic view remains and we still have conflict in our mind.

From the Buddhist point of view, any information received through the five –sense consciousnesses is always distorted by dualistic grasping. It's like an optical illusion. It registers in our consciousness and we believe that what we are seeing is true. Actually, it's an unreal distortion and it gives birth to every other delusion.

Consequently, the Buddhist attitude towards data received through the five – sense consciousnesses is one of mistrust. You cannot rely on the judgements of good and bad that come through your senses-they always give you a dualistic, distorted impression.

The experience of non –duality itself is in the nature of love. The emotional tone of love is lower during meditative absorption in non – duality but its nature is essentially present. Most people's love is biased and dualistic. Love characterized by non-duality feels no partiality.

It is extremely important that we make an effort to lead a spiritual life while, as human beings, we have the opportunity to pursue inner methods that bring peace of mind.

It is common experience that happiness does not arise from external factors alone. If we look carefully into our own daily lives, we will easily see that this is true. In addition to external factors, there are also inner factors that come into play to establish happiness within us.

If external development were all it took to produce lasting peace within us, then those who were rich in material possessions would have more peace and happiness, while those who were poor would have less. But life is not always like this. There are many happy people with few riches and many wealthy people who are very unhappy.

The problem is that samsara is a circle, a wheel. Its function is to circle our aggregates i.e. our body and mind continue from this life into next, we did not do the work necessary to liberate our mind from the unsubdued minds and karma. Therefore, our mind and body are still in the nature of suffering; we're still experiencing the same problems over and over again. Had we liberated ourselves from the unsubdued mind and karma we would never have had to suffer again; it would have been impossible. It would have been impossible. Once we are free from samsaric suffering from the bondage of karma and the unsubdued mind, we can never suffer again. If we had liberated ourselves before, there would have been no reason for us to suffer now; our mind and body would not have been in the nature of suffering.

If we didn't have a samsaric body, we wouldn't have needed a house, clothing, food or other temporal needs. There would have been no need to worry, make preparations, collect many possessions, chase money, have hundreds of different clothes to wear in the different seasons, have hundreds of shoes, engage in business, and so forth. We would have had none of these problems. But we do have a samsaric body, therefore, our entire life, from rebirth to death, is kept busy taking care of it.

Even in this life, much of our happiness is received in dependence upon the kindness of others. Not only humans but many animals work hard and suffer for our happiness; many die or are killed for us. For example, in order to produce rice in a field, many people work and suffer under the sun many creatures are killed and so forth. The happiness of each day of our life completely depends on the kindness of other sentient beings.

As human beings, we have great opportunity to repay this kindness. They are ignorant and we are able to understand the nature of reality and help all sentient beings by liberating them from suffering.

The path is the holy Dharma and the essence of the path is the good heart. The greatest, highest good heart is bodhicitta – the determination to become a Buddha in order to liberate all sentient beings from suffering. This is the supreme good heart. This is what we should generate.

Bodhicitta And Wisdom

The enlightened attitude, bodhicitta, which has love and compassion as its basis, is the essential seed producing the attainment of Buddhahood. Therefore, it is a subject that should be approached with the pure thought

If we want to attain the state of full enlightenment of Buddhahood our innermost practice must be the cultivation of bodhicitta.

Although bodhicitta is the principal cause of Buddhahood, bodhicitta must unite with wisdom, or meditation on emptiness, is capable of attaining Buddhahood. One without the other does not bring full enlightenment—even though bodhicitta is the essential energy that produces Buddhahood, throughout the stages of its development it should be combined with meditation on emptiness. In the Prajnaparamita Sutras (Perfection of Wisdom), where the Buddha spoke most extensively on emptiness, we are constantly reminded to practise our meditation on emptiness within the context of bodhicitta.

However, the spiritual effects of receiving teachings on bodhicitta are quite limited if we lack a certain spiritual foundation. Consequently, most teachers insist that we first cultivate various preliminary practices within ourselves before approaching this higher precept. If we want to go to the university, we must first learn to read and write. Merely hearing about meditation on love, compassion and bodhicitta does leave a favourable imprint on our mental continuum, but for the teaching to really produce a definite inner transformation, we have to meditate extensively on preliminaries such as the perfect human rebirth, impermanence and death, the nature of karma and samsara, refuge and the higher trainings in ethics, meditation and wisdom.

What precisely is bodhicitta? It is the mind strongly characterized by the aspiration 'For the sake of all sentient beings, I must attain the state of full enlightenment.' While it's easy to repeat these words to ourselves, bodhicitta is much deeper than that. It is a quality we cultivate systematically within our mind. Merely holding the thought 'I must attain enlightenment for the sake of benefiting others' in mind, without first cultivating its prerequisite causes, stages and basic foundations, will not give birth to bodhicitta.

The Benefits Of Bodhicitta

What are the benefits of generating bodhicitta? If we know the qualities of good food, we will attempt to obtain, prepare and eat it. Similarly, when we hear of the great qualities of bodhicitta we will seek to learn the methods and practices for generating it.

The immediate benefit of generating bodhicitta within our mind-stream is that we enter the great vehicle leading to Buddhahood and gain the title of bodhisattva, a child of the Buddhas. It does not matter what we look like, how we dress, how wealthy or powerful we are, whether or not we have clairvoyance or miraculous powers, or how learned we are— as soon as we generate bodhicitta, we become bodhisattvas. Regardless of our other qualities, if we do not have bodhicitta we are not bodhisattvas. Even a being with bodhicitta who takes rebirth in an animal body is respected by all Buddhas as a bodhisattva.

The great sages of the lesser vehicle possess numberless wonderful qualities but in terms of nature, a person who has developed even the initial stages of bodhicitta surpasses them. This is similar to the way that the child of a universal monarch who, although only an infant possessing no qualities of knowledge or power, is accorded higher status than any scholar or minister in the realm.

In terms of conventional benefit, all the happiness and goodness that exists comes from bodhicitta. As a result of the birth of buddhas and bodhisattvas, great waves of enlightened energy spread throughout the universe, influencing sentient beings to create positive karma. This positive karma, in turn, brings them much benefit and happiness.

How To Develop Bodhicitta

How do we develop bodhicitta? There are two major methods. The first of these, the six causes and one effect, applies six causal meditations—recognizing that all sentient beings were once our own mother, a mother's kindness, repaying such kindness, love, compassion and the extraordinary thought of universal responsibility—to produce one result: bodhicitta. The second technique is the meditation in which we directly change self-cherishing into the cherishing of others.

In order to practise either of these methods of developing bodhicitta, we must first develop a sense of equanimity towards all living beings. We must transcend seeing some beings as close friends, others as disliked or hated enemies, and the rest as merely unknown strangers. Until we have developed equanimity for all beings, any meditation we do in an attempt to develop bodhicitta will not be effective. For example, if we want to paint a mural on a wall, we must first get rid of all the cracks and lumps on its surface. Similarly, we cannot create the beautiful bodhicitta within our mind until it has been purified of the distortions of seeing others as friend, enemy or stranger.

The attitude Of Discrimination

The way we apply this discrimination to others is quite automatic, and a result, whenever we see somebody we have labelled 'friend', attachment arises and we respond with warmth and kindness. Why have we labelled this person 'friend'? It is only because on some level or other this person has benefitted or supported us. Alternatively., whenever we encounter somebody we have labelled 'enemy,' aversion arises and we respond with coldness and anger. The reason is again because that person once harmed or threatened us in some way. Similarly, when we encounter somebody who has neither helped nor harmed us, we apply the label 'stranger' and have no feelings for that person one way or the other.

However, if we examine this method of discriminating among others, we will quickly see that it is an extremely unstable process. Even in this life, people once regarded as friends become enemies, and enemies often become friends. In the countless lives we have taken since beginningless time while spinning on the wheel of life, there is not one sentient being who has consistently been either friend or enemy.

A friend who mistreats us quickly becomes an enemy and an enemy who helps us soon becomes a new-found friend. So, who is really the friend and who is the enemy? Instead of responding to others on the basis of the ephemeral benefit or harm they bring us, we should meditate that all have alternately benefitted and harmed us in the stream of our infinite past lives, and thus abandon superficial discriminations.

The root cause of this discriminating mind is the self-cherishing attitude, the thought that makes us consider ourselves more important than others. As a result of self-cherishing, we develop

attachment to those who help us and aversion to those who cause us problems. This, in turn, causes us to create countless negative karmas trying to support the 'helpers' and overcome the 'banners'. Thus, we bring great, suffering upon ourselves and others, both immediately and in future lives, as the karmic seeds of these actions ripen into suffering experiences.

A teaching says,

All happiness in the world arises from cherishing
others; every suffering arises from self-cherishing.

Why is this so? From self-cherishing comes the wish to further oneself even at others' expense. Self-cherishing is responsible for every conflict from family problems to international wars, and for all the negative karma thus created.

What are the results of cherishing others? If we cherish others, we won't harm or kill them. This is conducive to our own long life. When we cherish others, we are open to and empathetic with them and live in generosity—this is a karmic cause of our own future prosperity. If we cherish others, even when somebody harms or creates problems for us, we are able to abide in love and patience—a karmic cause of a beautiful form in future lives. These conditions themselves bring joy and happiness.

Looking at it another way, cherishing others is the proper and noble approach to take. In this life, everything that comes to us is, directly or indirectly, due to the kindness of others. We buy food from others in the market; the clothing we wear and the houses we live in depend upon the help of others

Also, any meditation teaching we receive has come from the Buddha through the kindness of sentient beings. The Buddha taught in order to benefit sentient beings; if there were no sentient beings he would not have taught. Therefore, in the Bodhisattvacharyavatara, Shantideva comments that in terms of kindness, sentient beings are equal to the Buddhas.

If we look at happiness and harmony, we will find its cause to be universal caring. The cause of unhappiness and disharmony is the self-cherishing attitude.

At one time, the Buddha was an ordinary person like us. Then he abandoned self-cherishing and replaced it with universal caring and entered the path to Buddhahood. Because we still cling to the self-cherishing mind, we are left behind in samsara, benefiting neither ourselves nor others.

One of the Jataka Tales—accounts of the Buddha's previous lives—tells the story of an incarnation in which the Buddha was a huge turtle that took pity on some shipwreck victims and carried them to shore on its back. Once ashore, the exhausted turtle fell into a faint but as he slept he was attacked by thousands of ants. Soon the biting of the ants woke the turtle up, but he saw that if he were to move, he would kill innumerable creatures. Therefore, he remained still and offered his body to the insects as food. This is the depth to which the Buddha cherished living beings.

Therefore, we should deeply contemplate the benefits of cherishing others and try to develop an open, loving attitude towards all living beings.

Some people feel great compassion for friends or relatives in trouble but none for unpleasant people or enemies. It is merely a form of attachment. True compassion does not discriminate between beings; it regards all equally.

Similarly, true love is the desire to maintain the happiness of all beings impartially, regardless of whether we like them or not. Spiritual love is of two main types: that merely possessing equanimity and that possessing the active wish to maintain others' happiness.

In brief, we should have the wish to help others maintain their happiness and separate them from suffering, regardless of whether they have acted as friend or enemy to us. Moreover, we should develop a personal sense of responsibility for their happiness. This is called the 'special' or 'higher' thought and is marked by a strong sense of responsibility for the welfare of others. It is like taking the responsibility of going to the market to get somebody exactly what he needs instead of just sitting, reflecting on how nice it would be if he had what he wanted. We take upon ourselves the responsibility of actually) fulfilling others' requirements.

Bodhicitta is born from the special thought of universal responsibility—the thought of benefiting others by oneself alone. To drink water, we must have both the desire to drink and a container for the water. The wish to benefit others by placing them in Buddhahood is like the desire to drink, and the wish to attain enlightenment oneself in order to benefit them in this way is like the container. Because spiritual knowledge is not gained from books or without cause, its cause must

be cultivated. This means training properly under a fully qualified spiritual master and generating the practices as instructed.

Merely hearing about bodhicitta is very beneficial because it provides a seed for the development of the enlightened spirit. However, cultivation of this seed to fruition requires careful practice. In order for our teacher's presence to be of maximum benefit, we should learn the correct attitudes and actions for cultivating an effective guru-disciple relationship. Then step-by-step, the seeds of bodhicitta our teacher plants within us can grow to full maturity and unfold the lotus of enlightenment within us.

The most important step in spiritual growth is the first: the decision to avoid evil and cultivate goodness within our stream of being. On the basis of this fundamental discipline, every spiritual quality becomes possible, even the eventual perfection of Buddhahood.

Each of us has the potential to do this; each of us can become a perfect being. All we have to do is direct our energy towards learning and then enthusiastically practice the teachings. As bodhicitta is the very essence of all the Buddha's teachings, we should make every effort to realize it.

